

Results from the Zurich sea water (ZSW) intercomparison study for U- and Pu-isotopes[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Approximately 350L of sea water samples were collected to prepare a large volume (Zurich Sea Water, ZSW) intercomparison sample for ^{236}U and other actinides. Here we report the results of the intercomparison study for U- and Pu-isotopes. ZSW was processed in six different chemistry labs and measured on five AMS systems and one MC-ICP-MS system, respectively. The analysis of the reported U-isotopic data shows that the scatter, indicated by the one sigma uncertainty for a single measurement, of the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratios and the ^{236}U , ^{238}U -concentrations is 5 % and 3 %, respectively. A Chi-squared analysis shows that the external error (lab-scatter) is 1–2 % and 3 % for the ^{236}U , ^{238}U -concentrations and the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratios, respectively.

The fact that ZSW has been characterized by many different (A)MS labs makes it a valuable internal standard for quality control for the analysis of anthropogenic U- and Pu-isotopes in seawater.

1. Introduction

The long-lived anthropogenic U-isotope ^{236}U ($T_{1/2} = 23.4$ Myr) and other actinide isotopes (e.g. Pu-isotopes and ^{233}U) are increasingly used in oceanographic studies to trace ocean currents and determine mixing ratios of water masses, or to identify the source of an anthropogenic contamination [1–6]. This success is supported by substantial developments in accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS) that allow the fast, precise, and almost background free determination of Pu- and U-isotopes in environmental samples [7–10]. The success of compact, low energy AMS systems in actinide research is not limited to U and Pu isotopes alone, it also triggered several studies relying on the highly sensitive and selective detection of the minor actinides (e.g. Np-, Am-, and Cm-isotopes) in environmental and biological samples [11–17]. Worldwide, the number of AMS systems capable of performing actinide measurements at environmental levels is increasing [18–20] and only recently, the ability to perform competitive analyses of ^{236}U and other actinides with the compact 300 kV AMS system MILEA has been reported [21]. With the number of AMS systems increasing the question arises of how accurate those measurements are, particularly when performed on different systems, applying different radiochemical methods, and using different internal standards for normalization. Here we report on the results of an intercomparison experiment for ^{236}U and Pu-isotopes carried out with a large volume sea water sample.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample treatment and preparation (pre shipment)

The sea water used for this experiment was collected in 2011 during the Fenice 2011 cruise [22] which took place from 25 October to 11 November 2011 in the Tyrrhenian Sea (Fig. 1). A total of about 350L of sea water was collected in 35 ten-liter plastic canisters, intended for $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ analysis at ETH Zurich. Unfortunately, the sample labels were not readable any more when they arrived at ETH Zurich. Instead of discarding the samples we decided to combine them and use the sea water as a large volume intercomparison sample for ^{236}U and the actinides.

The sea water was pumped through 0.45 μm membrane filters using a peristaltic pump. Filters were exchanged after every second sample and the filtered sea water was collected in a 500L plastic tank that has been previously rinsed with deionized water. By adding concentrated nitric acid (p.a.) the pH value was adjusted to 3.0 ± 0.5 using pH indicator strips. After some months of equilibration pH was checked again. Then the seawater was filled into 35 ten-liter plastic cubitainers before shipment to the participating labs. The sample was named Zurich Sea Water intercomparison sample (ZSW).

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2.2. Sample processing and analysis (post shipment)

The primary goal of the intercomparison study was to collect information on the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratio and the ^{236}U and ^{238}U concentrations of ZSW. Nevertheless, the labs were asked to provide additional information on concentration of other actinides, if possible. Depending on request, one or two ZSW-cubitainers were sent out to each participating laboratory. Each participant was asked to apply their standard sample processing procedures for uranium and other actinides. Similarly, the AMS labs were asked to use their standard instrumental setups, measurement routines and to employ their own in-house reference materials.

2.3. Data evaluation and analysis

ZSW has been processed in six different chemistry labs and actinide results were reported from five different AMS systems and from one Multi Collector Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry system (MC-ICP-MS). Results from the different participants and instruments are presented in an anonymized way. In all figures, different labs are indicated by different colors and different (A)MS systems are identified by different symbols. Several combinations of colors and symbols are possible as one laboratory can prepare samples that are measured on different AMS systems or one AMS lab can measure samples prepared in different labs. For those labs that agreed, the identities of the prep labs and (A)MS facilities are revealed in [Table S2](#) in the [supplementary information](#).

In total, 26 data reports were returned, while one data report may include information on several isotopes or isotopic ratios e.g., on the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratio, the concentrations of ^{236}U and ^{238}U , etc. Throughout

the paper, the term isotopic ratio always refers to an atom ratio. In all figures of this paper, each data point represents one reported result. Reported data points were not combined or averaged.

For each set of isotope concentrations or isotopic ratios reported by the different labs, the error weighted mean and the standard deviation of the weighted mean was calculated using Eq (1) and Eq (2):

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum_i y_i \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}}{\sum_i \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{Y})^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}}{\sum_i \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}} \quad (2)$$

Accordingly, the reduced Chi-Squared value for each data set is given by:

$$X_{red}^2 = \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{Y})^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}}{(n-1)} \quad (3)$$

where n is the total number of reported data points (y_i) for each isotope or isotopic ratio and i indicates one single reported result including its one sigma uncertainty.

The upper and lower limits for X_{red}^2 were calculated for each data set using the χ^2 -distribution with $(n-1)$ degrees of freedom using a 95 % confidence interval. In case the scatter of the data set (and therefore the X_{red}^2 value) exceeded the range calculated from the χ^2 -distribution, it was assumed that the dataset contains some additional uncertainty e.g., introduced by the different labs, due to, for example, different chemical procedures, different AMS-techniques or standards, etc. In this case, an external scatter was added to each data point according to EQ (4):

Fig. 1. Cruise track of the Fenice 2011 cruise (. Source: Google Maps)

$$\sigma_{i, \text{tot}}^2 = \sigma_i^2 + (y_i \cdot \sigma_{\text{ext}\%})^2 \quad (4)$$

The relative external error ($\sigma_{\text{ext}\%}$, Table S1) was varied until the X_{red}^2 value (EQ (3)) equaled the upper value of the according X^2 -distribution. We note that this implies the assumption that the external scatter is represented by an additional (normal distributed) statistical fluctuation and not by a systematic error (e.g., due to different standards used for normalization).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results for the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ (and $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$) ratios

All participating labs reported results on the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratio of ZSW. In total, 26 data points from 6 different labs, 5 AMS systems, and 1 MC-ICP-MS were reported.

One AMS lab, however, indicated that their result is indicative only as they were still optimizing their laboratory protocols for ^{236}U and sample preparation suffered from low yield. These results (magenta triangle) for $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ (and for the concentrations of ^{236}U and ^{238}U) are shown for completeness only, and are not included in the calculation of the average value nor the Chi-squared distribution (Fig. 2 and Table S1). Also, the group providing $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ results measured with MC-ICP-MS considered their setup experimental at that stage and reported that the results might be systematically biased because they strongly rely on the performance and calibration of the secondary electron multiplier detector. We therefore decided not to include those results in the calculations as well (open purple hexagons, Fig. 2). We, nevertheless want to mention that the ICP-MS lab only used 1 L of sea water to perform their measurement and reported their data with a remarkable small uncertainty. This result demonstrates that MC-ICP-MS in general has the capability of analyzing $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratios in sea water at a level of 10^{-9} [23].

The remaining 22 data points from 5 labs measured on 5 different

AMS systems were all included in the following calculations (Fig. 2 and Table S1). Based on these data, the average value for the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratio is $(1689 \pm 77) \times 10^{-12}$. The X_{red}^2 value of 2.86 for this result indicates that the reported uncertainties do not fully explain the scatter of the data set based on a 95 % confidence level. The statistical analysis indicates that an external scatter of 2.0 % is needed to explain the distribution of the data. Taking into account that the typical uncertainty of a $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ measurement in a surface sea water sample with AMS is 3–5 % this is an acceptable result. It indicates that the contributing 5 labs and 5 AMS systems are able to provide consistent results on $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ in sea water that agree within 5 % or less.

Three labs provided additional information on the $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$ ratio of ZSW (Fig. 3, Table S1). The sample was analyzed on two different AMS systems only, therefore statistics on the $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$ results is limited. Nevertheless, the data from Lab 1 shows a clear discrepancy from the results reported by Lab 2 and Lab 3. In this lab, the intercomparison sample was processed and measured together with other sea water samples that were spiked with about 1 pg of ^{233}U , each. The fact that the two results are significantly higher than the ones reported by Lab 2 and Lab 3 indicates that the samples processed in Lab 1 were probably contaminated by the ^{233}U spike either during chemical processing in the lab or suffered from cross-contamination during the AMS measurement. An alternative explanation would involve surviving $^{232}\text{Th}^{3+}$ molecules due to insufficiently high stripper pressure [24]. The results on $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$ reported from Lab 1 were therefore excluded from the calculation of the average. For the remaining six data points from two different labs, measured on one AMS system an average value of $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U} = (0.67 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-2}$ was calculated.

The statistical analysis of the results indicates that the reported uncertainties are in accordance with the scatter of the data points. Therefore, no additional external uncertainty is needed to explain the scatter of the data points. It has to be noted that the determination of ^{233}U in sea water is almost always limited by counting statistics and uncertainties of about 10 % are common for AMS analyses of $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$.

Fig. 2. Reported results for $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ of ZSW. Datapoints marked with a star (*) were not included in the average.

Fig. 3. Reported results for $^{233}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ of ZSW. Data points marked with a star (*) were not included in the average (see text for details).

Fig. 4. Reported results for ^{236}U -concentration of ZSW.

Since the results were produced by only one AMS lab no statement can be made about inter-comparability of $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$ between different AMS systems. The average $^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$ ratio reported in this study, nevertheless, may serve as indicative value for future AMS analyses and inter-comparisons. Based on the average ^{236}U concentration of ZSW presented in the next section, an average ^{233}U concentration of $(1.0 \pm 0.1) \times 10^5$ at/kg in ZSW is estimated.

3.2. Results for the ^{236}U - and ^{238}U -concentrations

Eighteen results were reported for the concentrations of ^{236}U and ^{238}U , respectively (Fig. 4, Fig. 5). The number of reported data points is smaller compared to $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ because not all labs (i) used a spike (typically ^{233}U) that allows determining the concentration of these isotopes by isotopic dilution or (ii) determined the concentration of ^{238}U separately in an aliquot of the sample (typically by ICP-MS). In total, three labs reported ^{236}U and ^{238}U concentration results that were measured on four different AMS systems.

The reported data on the ^{236}U concentration scatters by 3.5 % around its average value of 15.5×10^6 at/kg. The statistical analysis (Table S1, Fig. 4) shows that an external uncertainty of 1.8 % is needed to explain the scatter of the data points compared to their reported uncertainties. This result is very similar to the $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratios where the external uncertainty was estimated to 2 %. Also in this case, the results indicate that the participating AMS labs are able to produce consistent data for ^{236}U concentrations typical for surface sea water within an uncertainty of 4 % or better.

The reported data on the ^{238}U concentration of ZSW scatters by 2.7 % around the average value of $3.67 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and statistical analysis indicates an external error of 1 % (Fig. 5, Table S1). For the determination of the ^{238}U concentration by the different participating laboratories two independent methods were applied. While Lab 1 and Lab 4 used a ^{233}U spike to determine both, ^{236}U and ^{238}U concentrations by isotopic dilution, Lab 2 analyzed ^{238}U by ICP-MS in an aliquot of the sample. The fact that the reported ^{238}U concentrations for ZSW determined by two

independent methods agree well, indicates that the reported results are not only precise but also accurate within an uncertainty of 3 % or less.

3.3. Results for Pu-isotopes

In addition to the information of U-isotopes three labs reported results on ^{239}Pu -, and ^{240}Pu -concentrations and on the $^{240}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ ratio (Fig. 6, Table S1).

The results were produced on three different AMS systems and average values of $(1.19 \pm 0.06) \times 10^6$ at/kg and $(6.17 \pm 0.19) \times 10^6$ at/kg are calculated for ^{240}Pu and ^{239}Pu , respectively. All labs added a ^{242}Pu spike to the sample in order to determine the concentration of ^{239}Pu and ^{240}Pu by isotopic dilution. The statistical analysis shows that no or only negligible (<1%) external uncertainty has to be added to the results. One lab also analyzed the sample without adding a spike. Therefore, for this preparation only information on the isotopic ratio was reported. This preparation, however, suffered from a low chemical yield and low counting rates during the measurement. Therefore, the reported uncertainty is relatively large. In a similar way as for Pu concentrations, for the ratio measurements of $^{240}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ no external uncertainty is needed to explain the scatter of the data points around their average value of (0.19 ± 0.01) at/at. In summary, the results for Pu-isotopes of the intercomparison sample reported by three labs and measured on three AMS systems indicate that all participating labs are able to produce consistent results for Pu-concentrations and isotopic ratios in sea water with 3–5 % uncertainty.

4. Summary and Conclusion

The main goal of this study was to perform an intercomparison study for the analysis of $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ in sea water. For this purpose, a large volume Zurich Sea Water (ZSW) intercomparison sample was produced and sent out to all participating labs. Results on $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ for the ZSW sample have been returned from 6 different labs and measurements were performed on 5 different AMS systems and on one MC-ICP-MS system,

Fig. 5. Reported results for ^{238}U -concentration of ZSW. Data points marked with a star (*) were not included in the average (see text for details).

Fig. 6. Reported results for ^{239}Pu and ^{240}Pu concentrations and the $^{240}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ ratio of ZSW.

respectively. Additional information was reported by the participating labs regarding the concentrations of ^{236}U , ^{238}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{240}Pu and on their isotopic ratios ($^{233}\text{U}/^{236}\text{U}$ and $^{239}\text{Pu}/^{240}\text{Pu}$).

The results collected from all participating labs for ^{236}U -, ^{238}U -, ^{239}Pu -, ^{240}Pu -concentrations and $^{239}\text{Pu}/^{240}\text{Pu}$ - and $^{236}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ -isotopic ratios agree well within 3–5 % uncertainty.

A Chi-squared analysis of the scatter of the data shows that the external scatter for all concentrations and isotopic ratios is equal or below 2 %. This shows that all participating labs are able to perform precise ^{233}U -, ^{236}U -, ^{238}U -, and ^{239}Pu -, ^{240}Pu -isotope analyses (including their isotopic ratios) in ocean surface water samples with an uncertainty of 3–5 %.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2025.165750>.

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